

Techniques in Magnetic Resonance Imaging and the Applications of Diffusion Based Imaging

Review: Topics in Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has established itself as an essential tool in clinical medicine for both diagnosis and monitoring of disease and injury. It provides two major advantages over other imaging techniques including x-ray and CT; the first is safety due to the lack of ionising radiation, the second is the enhanced soft tissue contrast as images can be weighted based on multiple MRI parameters which vary between different tissue. This review will examine the physics used to create these images. This includes the creation and detection of the magnetic resonance signal, the spatial locating of the signal to form an image and the pulse sequences which are used to enhance the image contrast for diagnosis. A large amount of the imaging is based upon the detection of proton density found within water in the body. The review will also go on to explore the techniques of Diffusion Weighted Imaging and Diffusion Tensor Imaging based upon the diffusion, or lack of diffusion, of this water. This includes their applications to the diagnosis of ischaemic stroke and pancreatic lesions. Improvements to diffusion-based imaging are also considered in the context of the Human Connectome Project which uses tractography to map out the structural connectivity of the brain.

Forming and Detecting an MR signal

As a diagnostic tool MRI is extremely powerful as emphasis, in the form of contrast, can be placed on certain tissues. This was largely inspired by Damadian who, in 1971, discovered that T1, a variable in Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), was significantly longer in cancerous tissue than the corresponding healthy tissue[1]. MRI techniques are now well established and based on imaging the protons in our bodies with the largest source of these being the hydrogen nuclei in water, which makes up around 70% of our tissue[2].

Protons possess a magnetic moment so behave like tiny bar magnets. When a uniform magnetic field is applied, protons can be understood, classically, to align either parallel or antiparallel to the field. As illustrated in figure 1, a small excess align parallel to the field so that the net sum produces a magnetization vector of strength M_0 along the z-axis. In MRI, the field, B_0 , (typically 1.5-3T for clinical usage) is produced using superconductors to avoid the energy loss of traditional wires.

Figure 1: Distribution of protons in a uniform magnetic field, B_0 , applied along the z direction. The net sum of proton magnetization produces an overall magnetization $(0,0,M_0)$ [3]

To form an MR signal radio frequency (RF) pulses are applied in the plane perpendicular to the field. The pulses perturb the magnetization vector away from equilibrium[4] and cause it to precess around the z-axis due to the resulting gyroscopic motion, as shown in figure 2. The rate of the precession is given by the Larmor frequency, ω_0 , where

$$\omega_0 = \gamma B_0 \quad (1)$$

and γ is the gyromagnetic ratio of the proton. Precessing protons emit a weak radio signal which, when surrounded by an RF coil, will induce a current of the same frequency[5][6]. This output signal yields information about the protons.

Figure 2: Precession of the magnetization vector, \mathbf{M} , around the z-axis and the resulting output signal at ω_0 . The component in the transverse plane, M_T , also rotates at ω_0 , the longitudinal component, M_L , is stationary. [3]

To achieve resonance, the input RF pulse must be corotating with the magnetization vector at ω_0 . Viewed in the rotating frame, the pulse applies a constant torque to the magnetisation, tilting it towards the x-y plane. The angle of tilt, α , is given by $\alpha = \gamma B_1 t$ where B_1 is the amplitude of the pulse and t is its duration.

A more complete description including mathematical details of signal generation may be found in Keeler[7].

Relaxation Mechanisms

The application of a pulse changes the local magnetic field, and it takes time for the magnetization vector to relax back to equilibrium along +z. The relaxation occurs by two mechanisms outlined in figure 3.

The first is spin-lattice relaxation which has a decay constant of T1. This relaxation describes the return of the tilt angle to zero as the magnetization recovers to the +z-axis. This is described mathematically by the Bloch equation[9]

$$\frac{dM_L}{dt} = \frac{M_0 - M_L}{T_1} \quad (2)$$

The second mechanism is spin-spin relaxation which has a decay constant of T2. This relaxation describes dephasing of transverse magnetization, into components in the x-y plane. This is described by a similar Bloch equation[9].

$$\frac{dM_T}{dt} = \frac{M_0 - M_T}{T_2} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Illustration of the T1 and T2 decay processes. (A) The magnetization is in equilibrium along +z. (B) An RF pulse is applied perturbing it to a flip angle of θ . (C, D) T2 decay causes the perpendicular component to dephase in the x-y plane. (E) T1 decay reduces the flip angle back to zero and returns the magnetization to equilibrium.[8]

T2 decay is caused by local inhomogeneities in the field due to spin interactions between protons. However, additional inhomogeneities are also present due to the application of magnetic field gradients and the engineering restrictions of creating a perfectly uniform magnetic field. This leads to Free

Induction Decay (FID) which has a time constant of T2*, much quicker than T2. This limits the T2 decay from being observed and lead to the development of the spin echo pulse sequence.

Creating Contrast

T1, T2 and proton density vary between different tissue, therefore the output signal depends on the tissue being imaged. Pulse sequences are used to create contrast by weighting the images with these parameters. For example, T1-weighted images are used to study Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy due to increased fat uptake in the muscle and a stronger T1 signal compared to unaffected muscle[10].

Figure 4 shows the Carr-Purcell-Meiboom-Gill (CPMG) spin echo pulse sequence. Unlike T2 decay, T2* decay is reversible and the additional dephasing that it causes is cancelled out by the 180° refocussing pulse. This results in the T2 envelope shown in figure 5.

T1 decay will return the longitudinal magnetization to equilibrium along +z. When it returns, the sequence will have to be restarted as the equilibrium output signal is zero. The time between each pulse sequence is known as TR, the repetition time.

The choices of TE and TR determine the weighting in the image. This is most easily understood by considering the signal loss between echoes given by

$$S = S_0(1 - e^{-\frac{TR}{T_1}})e^{-\frac{TE}{T_2}} \quad (4)$$

For example, to create a T2-weighted image it would make sense to use a long TR to remove emphasis on T1. The advantages of different weighting can be viewed in figure 6.

Spin echo is just one of many available pulse sequences and is discussed here as it is the basis for pulse sequences used in diffusion imaging. Detail on other common sequences may be found in McRobbie[13].

Figure 6: Scans of a left frontal lobe tumour and their respective weighting. PD refers to proton density[12].

Figure 4: Spin-Echo pulse sequence. (a) A 90° pulse flips the magnetization vector into the x-y plane. (b) FID occurs and the magnetization begins dephasing. (c) After a time τ , a 180° pulse is applied reversing the directions of the vector in the x-y plane. (d) The dephasing also reverses and becomes rephasing. (e) At a time 2τ or TE the magnetization is fully rephased creating an echo in the signal. (f-i) The process is repeated with another 180° pulse leading to a second echo. [2]

Figure 5: RF input (top line) and the resulting output signal (bottom line) for a spin echo sequence. Each echo decays rapidly due to FID and T_2 can be measured from the overall envelope. [11]

Spatial Locating

To produce an image, the output signal must also encode the location of the protons that created it. This is achieved using magnetic field gradients.

Consider a magnetic field with a gradient $\mathbf{G}(t)$. The field in a direction \mathbf{r} is

$$B_G(t) = \mathbf{G}(t) \cdot \mathbf{r} \quad (5)$$

and so, depends linearly on the position. Equation 1 tells us that the output signal frequency therefore also depends on position. This idea was used by Lauterbur[14] to create the first MRI image in 1973, displayed in figure 7.

However, Lauterbur's method was slow and not suitable for clinical imaging. This relied on the development of rapid image acquisition techniques and the formalism of k-space imaging by Mansfield in 1977[16]. Lauterbur and Mansfield shared the 2003 Nobel prize in medicine for their work.

When a gradient, $\mathbf{G}(t)$, is applied to a spin it causes an additional precession of $\gamma \mathbf{G}(t) \cdot \mathbf{r}$ meaning precession rates increase uniformly along

Figure 7: Lauterbur's method of Zeugmatography. (a) The sample is formed from a larger tube of D_2O with two smaller tubes filled with H_2O . The projections show the magnetic field gradients applied in the x-z plane to obtain the data. (b) The final image displaying the locations of the protons in H_2O . It was recreated using tomographic methods already in place for x-rays.[14][15]

the gradient line. For spins initially in phase, the application of the gradient therefore creates a phase offset given by

$$\Phi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \gamma \left[\int_{t_0}^t \mathbf{G}(t') dt' \right] \cdot \mathbf{r} \quad (6)$$

where t_0 defines the start time of a pulse with duration t . This can then be rewritten as $\Phi = 2\pi \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}$.

With more mathematical detail found in Ansoorge[2], it can be shown that the output signal is now the Fourier transform of the proton density in k-space. By applying gradients in a method known as spin warp[17] and inverting the Fourier transform the spatial distribution of protons can be obtained creating an image.

The first gradient, known as the Slice Select (SS), is applied along an arbitrary direction, z' , causing the excitation frequency of the protons to depend on z' . An RF pulse with a narrow bandwidth is then applied so that only protons in a small z' range are excited. Ideally, the RF pulse has a sinc form so that a uniform slice of finite thickness is obtained.

Next, a Frequency Encode (FE) gradient is applied in the x' direction. This separates the slice into lines of equal frequency as displayed in figure 8.

Figure 8: The application of an FE gradient to a selected slice. The central line occurs when x' is zero so there is no additional precession. Each proton on a given dotted line precesses at the same frequency.[11]

Lastly, a short gradient pulse is applied in y' direction known as the Phase Encoding (PE) gradient. The short pulse creates a phase offset along the line due to the additional precession. For a pulse of duration Δt , $k_{y'}$ becomes $k_{y'} = k_{y'} + G_y \Delta t$, separating each point along the line in y' .

Overall, this method yields information on one line of k-space at a time. After a line is obtained, the RF pulse sequence is restarted, and the PE gradient is reapplied with a slightly different strength to move the signal to the next line. This is shown in figure 9a.

Figure 9: Acquisition paths in k-space. (a) Path for the spin warp technique, recording information one line at a time. (b) Path for Echo Planar Imaging (EPI). This records the entire image in a single excitation leading to much faster imaging. After the completion of each line a small PE gradient known as a “blip” is applied to move on to the next line. The FE gradient is reversed so the direction of acquisition alternates between lines.[2]

Diffusion Weighted Imaging

Diffusion Weighted Imaging (DWI) exploits differences in diffusion rates of water to create contrast. This is powerful in situations where cells may swell due to injury, restricting the flow of water. A notable example of this is the diagnosis of ischemia in cats[18] where DWI could make a diagnosis that T2-w imaging was unable to.

When water diffuses with Brownian motion, the protons will experience different magnetic field strengths due to the use of gradients in the field. Equation 6 tells us that the additional field experienced by diffusing protons causes a change in phase which can be highlighted by a Pulsed Gradient Spin Echo (PGSE) sequence shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: PGSE pulse sequence. Δ is the time between the centres of the diffusion sensitizing gradients and δ is their duration.[13]

The sequence is based on a spin-echo EPI (figure 9B) for rapid image acquisition, which is discussed in more detail later. Additionally, there is a strong gradient pulse applied before and after the refocussing 180° RF pulse. For a stationary proton, the first pulse creates additional phase which is then exactly cancelled by the second pulse after refocussing.

However, for a randomly diffusing proton, the additional phase gained due to its movement is not cancelled out after refocussing. This is because diffusion is irreversible and results in a decrease of the signal strength. The output signal is given by

$$S = S_0 e^{-bD} \quad (7)$$

where S_0 is the signal strength of a standard T2-w image, D is the Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC) of the tissue and b is feature of the gradient pulse[20] given by

$$b = \gamma^2 G^2 \delta^2 \left(\Delta - \frac{\delta}{3} \right) \quad (8)$$

Typically, an image with $b = 0 \text{ smm}^{-2}$ is recorded to account for T2 relaxation effects. The remaining images for diffusion weighting are then recorded with $b \approx 1000 \text{ smm}^{-2}$. Example images are

shown in figure 11 alongside a map of the ADC values.

DWI is used to diagnose a vast range of diseases including pancreatic lesions. The diffusion in malignant lesions is more restrictive than benign lesions[21] allowing for improved identification and grading of tumours[22].

Figure 11: DWI images and ADC maps of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) and pancreatic neuroendocrine carcinoma(PNEC). The PNEC has a lower ADC than PDAC so appears light blue on the ADC map. The restricted diffusion also causes the brighter signal on the DW image.[23]

Diffusion Tensor Imaging

DWI considers the isotropic diffusion of water; however, this is often not the case when the tissues being imaged are anisotropic. Here, the ADC may depend on the direction in which the diffusion sensitizing gradient is applied and it becomes a tensor value rather than a scalar.

The tensor is symmetric and can be fully obtained by making 7 measurements of D. The first is the $b = 0 \text{ smm}^2$ measurement, to remove T2 effects. The remaining 6 correspond to applying the diffusion sensitizing gradient in the orthogonal directions x, y, z and at 45° to each of the xy, yz, zx planes.

Once obtained the eigenvalues and eigenvectors can be directly calculated from the tensor with the principal eigenvector showing the preferred diffusion direction[13].

In axonal fibre bundles the diffusion of water is anisotropic, preferring to diffuse parallel to the length of the bundle than perpendicular to it[24]. The principal eigenvector therefore lies along the length of bundle. By connecting the principal eigenvectors in adjacent voxels, a continuous path can be formed showing the pathway of the neuronal connections. This technique is known as tractography, and an example is shown in figure 12.

Figure 12: Tractography image of the brain from the Human Connectome Project[25].

Tractography and the Human Connectome Project

The Human Connectome Project (HCP) was founded in 2009 with the aim of mapping out the functional and anatomical connectivity in a healthy human brain[26]. The project aided in several advancements in diffusion MRI techniques as tractography was the main method for understanding the “structural connectivity” between the white matter tracts and grey matter.

Tractography has limitations as it shows the preferred diffusion direction (PDD), not the orientation of the fibres. Therefore, when fibres intersect and bend it is difficult to follow their correct trajectory leading to false positives in the pathing. Examples of this are shown in figure 13.

Figure 13: Ambiguities in the mapping of axon geometry. Many different geometries result in the same diffusion tensor.[27].

To minimise these errors, data collection needed to improve the signal to noise ratio (SNR) and the resolution of the image. Primarily, this was achieved by using stronger diffusion gradients of 100mT/m compared to typical 40mT/m[25]. By

using a stronger gradient, the diffusion time, Δ , can be decreased without impacting the signal strength. This shortens the acquisition time and reduces the signal loss caused by T2 decay, improving the SNR achieved per unit time. This allows a reduction in the voxel size improving the spatial resolution. More detail on this can be found in Ugurbil[25].

A 300mT/m gradient was also considered, however, without increasing the slew rate this would take 3 times longer to produce, with the extra time negating the benefits of the stronger gradient. Limits on the slew rate exist due to peripheral nerve stimulation (PNS) caused by the large switching rates[28]. This prevents both large gradients and large slew rates being used simultaneously.

In this regard, more recent studies have shown the potential of head only scanners. By excluding the shoulders and torso there is a much higher PNS threshold allowing for consistent gradients of >200mT/m whilst maintaining a high slew rate[30][31].

Figure 14: Comparison of tractography resolution for varying magnetic field gradients. The resolution visibly improves with increased gradient strength[29].

Additionally, it was found there were no benefits to using a stronger B_0 field in the project. Although at stronger fields the signal strength improves due to a larger magnetization vector, this is balanced by a decrease of T2 leading to additional T2 decay and a reduction of SNR[29]. A more established 3T magnet was therefore selected instead of a newer 7T magnet[25].

Image collection times were also improved through the use of Multiband excitation (MB). When an SS gradient is applied the RF pulse is applied with multiple bands to excite multiple slices. The signals from all the excited slices are collected simultaneously by RF coils with different sensitivities. The output is then decomposed back to the individual slices. This improves the rate by a factor of the number of slices imaged.

Improving the rate minimises the risk of data corruption due to head movement during the shorter scan and allows time for more repeats to be taken. Three slices were used in the project due to safety limitations in the specific absorption rate

(SAR), the rate of RF energy absorption by the patient[29].

Overall, this significantly improved the performance of diffusion MRI and allowed for data collection from 1200 patients. This data base is actively being used in new research by the HCP, focussed on understanding how brain disorders, such as autism and Alzheimer's, alter the connection map.

Conclusion

This report introduces several of the basic principles used in MRI alongside the physics that aid and explain them. These form the foundations for how signals are generated and detected, and how contrast is created to improve diagnosis due to difference in the tissue parameters. Additionally, there is a focus on how MRI techniques are used in diffusion-based imaging which is often able to provide an accurate diagnosis in situations where injury leads to restricted water flow. Finally, the application of diffusion tensor imaging to tractography is considered in the context of the Human Connectome Project. With a goal of mapping out the network of connections in a healthy human brain, the project made several advancements in diffusion imaging techniques required to improve the signal to noise ratio and resolution of the data that is collected for tractography. This research led to the collection of data from 1200 patients which is being actively used to aid the understanding of several brain disorders including autism and Alzheimer's.

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